

DEVELOPMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF SOLAR HARVESTER: A PRAGMATIC APPROACH IN AGRICULTURE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The solar harvester offers a number of benefits including rapid harvesting of crops, reducing labour and the associated fuel costs involved in hiring of the workers. The present study developed a solar harvester and then evaluated its performance in a wheat field. The solar harvester mainly consisted of metallic frame, blades, solar panel, DC motors, battery, and wheels. The Field efficiency of the developed solar harvester was analysed using time and motion study method. The total grain losses (%), harvesting efficiency and cost of development of solar harvester were determined using mathematical formulas as recommended by previous studies. The results revealed that theoretical field capacity was 0.128 ha h^{-1} , the effective field capacity was 0.089 ha h^{-1} and field efficiency was 69.77%. The total grain losses were 3.01%, harvesting efficiency was 97.08% and the cost for development of machine was Rs.76000. The results demonstrated that the developed solar harvester will not only enhance the harvesting efficiency and reduce total grain losses but could potentially address the issues of increasing fuel costs and labor implementation for small land holding farmers..

INTRODUCTION

One of the major food grain crops in the world, including Pakistan, is wheat, which is used as a staple food for one third of the world's population. With an annual production of 27,293 thousand hectares and an average yield of $2,947 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, wheat is produced on an area of 21807 thousand hectares in Pakistan [1]. As 1/3 of the global populace depends on the wheat crop, there is dire need for adequate production of wheat [2]. Nevertheless, scientists have developed

several high yielding varieties, the productivity of wheat is still very low as compared to other countries owing to various factors including weather, land preparation, irrigation, fertilizers, and soil quality, etc [3]. Moreover, the harvesting of wheat crops is accomplished through hand tools, which in turn results in substantial loss of wheat grains [4], As fossil fuels rapidly diminish, their prices continue to rise, it is worth noting that approximately 510.387071

billion liters (equivalent to around 321 million barrels) of fine motor fuel were consumed in the USA in 2021, averaging about 369 million gallons per day [5]. Additionally, 88.2 billion liters of diesel were used annually, resulting in insignificant emissions detrimental to our environment and planet [6]. It is crucial to switch towards renewable energy resources, particularly solar energy. Solar energy, being the most abundant energy resource on Earth, with a continuous influx of 173,000 terawatts, surpasses global energy consumption by over 10,000 times. Harnessing this vast energy potential can greatly benefit our environment [7]. Harvesting crops manually is a labour-intensive and complex task, aggravated by a shortage of available workers. The process is time-consuming and inefficient. Although various harvesting machines are available in the market, they significantly reduce the time required for crop cutting of crops. However, their high costs and rental charges make them economically unfeasible for farmers. Over time, many scientists have modified the cutting process of harvesters to make harvesting operations easier. Nevertheless, those machines were utterly dependent on fossil fuels, which consume high costs and create environmental pollution. Therefore, it is crucial to design and develop a solar-powered harvester that would not only be cost-effective but may be environment-friendly [8]. Solar powered harvester rotates the cutter blade powered by solar energy. It is an improvement on cordless electric harvester. The harvester working on solar energy is actually based on the principles of early innovations of harvester. It produces the energy required to run the blades using a photovoltaic panel [9]. The energy needed for the earth's climatic system is sufficiently supplied by the sun. The earth only receives 2.551018 of the 5.681026 calories that the sun emits per minute, Only one millionth of all solar energy transmitted into species represented by this [10]. According to estimates, the total solar energy is 30,000 times more than the yearly global energy consumption. It is anticipated that a harvester powered by solar energy will address a number of concerns that conventional harvesters powered by IC engines and electrical actuators do not [11]. The harvester with Sun's energy supply is easier to employ, it has eliminated down time by frequent trips to the petrol stations for fill-ups and danger related with petrol spillage. Additionally, it

stops the harmful pollutants into the atmosphere that are caused by petrol spills and internal combustion engines [12]. The solar-powered harvester often contributes to a reduction in both the noise and air pollutants that are created by other types of harvesters. Additionally, it will assist in lowering the cost of operating and maintaining a harvester [13] [14]. During harvesting seasons, labour migration in non-agricultural sectors, labour shortages and crop harvesting costs are all challenging issues for the farmers [15]. Moreover, the harvesting is typically delayed during the tiring harvesting seasons due to a labour shortage, which reduces the production of other crops. Utilizing machines and farm labour to boost productivity and profitability of farming enterprises while using the least number of inputs is known as mechanized agriculture [16]. It offers a lot of potential advantages for consumers, farmers, and the economy as a whole. Agricultural technologies can boost economic output and cut down on the amount of time needed for agricultural production, processing, and transport. Jones et al. [17] noted that technology and mechanization can enhance work timing, lessen drudgery, increase labour productivity, and enhance food quality and quantity. An essential step in ensuring crop productivity, quality, and production costs is timely harvesting of the crops [18]. In order to prevent rain-related waste and to save valuable time for planting succeeding crops, the combine harvesting method with a wheat straw chopper should be used. The wheat straw crusher is a profitable piece of equipment, and its price needs to come down so that many farmers may afford and use it [19].

This study aims to design, develop and performance evaluation of solar harvester for wheat crop.

1. Research aim and methodology

The solar harvester was designed and developed at Workshop, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology (QUEST), Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan and its performance was evaluated at the farmer's field in the vicinity of university. Three plots of field were selected for analysing performance of solar harvester i.e. Plot 1. The experimental block of an area 1200 m² (60m x 20 m) was selected for evaluating the performance of solar harvester for

wheat crop. The experimental block was divided into three plots, each plot of 400 m² for evaluating the performance of solar harvester to harvest wheat crop. An area of experimental plots was measured with measuring tape. Three randomly selected small areas in each plot for determining total grain loss. The size of the small area (1.5m*1.5m) wooden frame was

thrown out randomly over three spots in each plot. After using solar harvester. Three plots were selected randomly (1.5m x 1.5m) and collected scattered spikes from selected areas to measure grain losses. Figure 1, while table 1 and table 2 material used in solar harvester and its specifications respectively.

Figure: 1. Pictorial view of solar harvester.

Table:1. Material used in solar harvester.

Components	Material
Frame	Mild steel
Shaft	High carbon steel
Crop divider	Galvanized iron sheet
Start wheel	Plastic
Handle	Mild steel
Chain	Carbon steel
Belt	Rubber
Bearing	Standard

Table: 2. Specifications of solar harvester.

Particulars	Specifications
Types of cutting	V shape 60°
Length of cutting blades	9.1 cm
Stroke length	8.25 inch cutting stroke length
Angle	0°
Number of blades	12

2.1 Physical properties

The soil moisture content, dry bulk density of soil and soil textural class were determined at three different locations from each plot before the start of experiment. The straw moisture content and grain moisture content were measured at the time of harvesting. The textural class of soil was estimated by Bouyoucos Hydrometer Technique.

2.2 Performance analysis

In order to evaluate various parameters involved in designing of solar harvester following parameters were calculated:

Field efficiency, operating speed, theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity, field efficiency, total grain losses and harvesting efficiency.

2. Results and discussion

The solar harvester was developed at the workshop, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Quaid e Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology, Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan. It operates based on a specific principle. It is equipped with panels arranged in a manner that allows them to efficiently capture high-intensity solar radiation from the sun. These panels perform the task of changing Sun photons into electrical energy. Subsequently, solar chargers employed to store this electrical current in storage batteries. The primary role of the solar charger is to amplify the current from the panels during the battery charging process.

Furthermore, it separates the batteries from the solar photovoltaic cells once they are fully charged, and also joins them when the battery charge is low. The batteries and motor are connected using connecting wires, and a mechanical circuit breaker switch is positioned between these components. This switch

controls the initiation and cessation of the motor's operation. The power from the motor is then transferred to the mechanism, causing the blade to slide across the fixed blade and effectively cut the wheat crop. The developed solar harvester machine was tested for its performance analysis in the farmer's field. This chapter contains the discussion of results obtained in the study. In this study theoretical field capacity was observed 0.128 ha h⁻¹, effective field capacity was 0.089 ha h⁻¹ and field efficiency was recorded 69.77%. This is consistent with Tsegaye (2020) [20], the theoretical field capacity of the reaper for wheat crop was 0.111 ha h⁻¹, the effective field capacity was 0.075 ha h⁻¹ and field efficiency of reaper harvesting machine was 67.57%. Similarly, the theoretical field capacity of the machine was 0.225ha h⁻¹, the effective field capacity was 0.182 ha h⁻¹, and field efficiency of reaper harvesting machine was 81%. Additionally, according to Sinha & Jogdand (2019) [21], the machine's average effective field capacity for harvesting wheat crops was 0.048 ha h⁻¹ at an average speed of 1.7 km/hr. For the wheat crop, the field efficiency was observed to be 71.2%. The self-propelled reaper's actual field capacity, as reported by Chavan et al. (2015) and Murumkar et al. (2014) [22], was 0.3 ha h⁻¹ with a 72% field efficiency.

3.1 Physical properties

Table 3 denotes the physical characteristics of soil, grain and straw. The average soil moisture content was 13.01%, dry bulk density of soil was 1.34 g/cm³, soil textural class was clay loam. The moisture content of grain was 10.11% and moisture content of straw was 9.22%.

Table: 3. Physical properties of soil, grain and straw.

Parameter	Value
Soil moisture content (%)	13.01
Dry bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.34
Sand (%)	27.4
Silt (%)	35.4
Clay (%)	37.2
Textural class	Clay loam
Grain moisture content (%)	10.11

Straw moisture contents (%)	9.22
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3.2 Theoretical field capacity

Figure 2 illustrates the theoretical field capacity of solar harvester at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3. The theoretical field capacity was 0.129, 0.128 and 0.127

ha h⁻¹ at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3, respectively. The highest theoretical field capacity was recorded at plot1, while lowest was seen at plot 3. The average theoretical field capacity was 0.128 hah⁻¹.

Figure: 2. Theoretical field capacity of solar harvester.

3.3 Effective field capacity

Figure 3 illustrates the effective field capacity of solar harvester at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3. The effective field capacity was 0.088, 0.089 and 0.090 ha h⁻¹ at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3, respectively. The highest effective field capacity was recorded at plot 3, while lowest was seen at plot 1. The mean effective field capacity was 0.089 hah⁻¹.

Figure: 3. Effective field capacity of solar harvester.

3.4 Field efficiency

Figure 4 portrays the field efficiency of solar harvester at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3. The field efficiency was 68.75, 69.63 and 70.92% at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3, respectively. The highest field efficiency was recorded at plot 3, while lowest was seen at plot 1. The average field efficiency was 69.77%.

Figure: 4. Field efficiency of solar Harvester.

3.5 Total grain losses

Figure 5 depicts the total grain losses of solar harvester at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3. Total grain losses were 3.03, 2.99 and 3.01% at plot 1, plot 2 and plot 3, respectively. The maximum total grain losses were noted at plot 1, while lowest were observed at plot 2. The average total grain losses were 3.01%.

Figure: 5.Total grain losses of solar harvester.

3.6 Harvesting efficiency

Figure 6 represents the harvesting efficiency of solar harvester at plot1, plot 2 and plot3. The harvesting efficiency was 97.06, 97.10 and 97.08% at plot1, plot 2 and plot 3, respectively. The maximum harvesting efficiency was noted at plot 2, while lowest was observed at plot 1. The average harvesting efficiency was 97.08%.

Figure 6. Harvesting efficiency of solar harvester.

3. Conclusion

The solar harvester was developed at the Workshop, Department of Mechanical Engineering, and Quaide-Awam University of Engineering, Science and Technology, Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan. The present study was carried out to design, develop and assess the performance of a solar harvester for wheat crop. The parameters of the study were theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity, field efficiency, total grain losses, and harvesting efficiency.

The highest theoretical field capacity was recorded at plot1, while lowest was seen at plot3. The average theoretical field capacity was 0.128 ha h^{-1} . The highest effective field capacity was recorded at plot 3, while lowest was seen at plot1. The mean effective field capacity was 0.089 hah^{-1} . The maximum total grain losses were noted at plot 1, while lowest were observed at plot 2. The average total grain losses were 3.01%. The total cost of solar harvester was found 76000 PKR. The developed solar harvester obtained the highest field efficiency in a clay loam soil and achieved maximum harvesting efficiency with reduced total grain losses for wheat crop.

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